

D5.5 - Service architecture providing fast access to the concepts held within semantic artifacts

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Deliverable Abstract

This document provides a summary of the outputs of and the activities carried out in EOOSC-Pillar's Task 5.5. The service architecture implemented in the task features a search engine that provides fast access to the concepts held within the semantic artifacts that are deemed valuable by the EOOSC-Pillar use cases, thus improving their FAIRness. Furthermore, it was integrated within the F2DS, developed in Task 5.1, to support a workflow enabling the annotation of datasets published by the community with concepts from said semantic artifacts.

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TERMINOLOGY

<https://eosc-portal.eu/glossary>

<i>Terminology/Acronym</i>	<i>Definition</i>
F2DS	Federated FAIR Data Space
NERC	Natural Environment Research Council
NVS	NERC Vocabulary Service
RDF	Resource Description Framework
SA	Semantic Artifact
XML	Extensible Markup Language

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1 Introduction

EOSC-Pillar is one of the INFRAEOSC 5b regional projects aiming at implementing the EOSC ecosystem through the connection with national initiatives. The works within the EOSC-Pillar project are organized in work packages covering among others 1. surveying and coordinating national initiatives, 2. integrating ready to use services, and 3. establishing and improving FAIR practices and services. These works are backed by community driven scientific use cases collected into work package 6 (WP6). The work package targeting FAIR practices in EOSC-Pillar (WP5) covers the promotion of FAIR practices by education and the technical enhancement of FAIR data(sets). This technical enhancement of FAIR data(sets) is achieved by creating and improving FAIR services. WP5 is subdivided into five tasks and the deliverable at hand is associated with the task T5.5 “Exploring metadata and ontologies, the foundations of cross-domain interoperability”. The main result of T5.5 is a service architecture that increases FAIRness of semantic artifacts and facilitates using them for semantically enriching (data-) resources, promoting semantic- and cross domain interoperability.

The work in the task started with a landscape analysis about the state and usage of semantic artifacts in the domains of the nine WP6 use cases. The evaluation of the landscape analysis led to the creation of an index based service architecture providing access to the content of the semantic artifact identified in the landscape analysis.

The final service architecture is built on a number of components, some that are part of the tasks T5.1 and T5.2 of WP5, namely the Federated Fair Data Space (F2DS) [1], and some that were setup for the task exclusively, namely instances of MongoDB, Elasticsearch and a data transformation pipeline written in Python and managed by Apache Airflow. The final service architecture has some unique characteristics: 1. It is geared towards very fast data retrieval in interactive usage scenarios. 2. The usage of the F2DS based harvesting infrastructure makes the registration of additional repositories for semantic artifacts an easy task. 3. The service infrastructure implements a search engine like ranking algorithm helping for (semi-) automatic annotation of datasets.

The service architecture has been validated in cooperation with use cases from WP6. An extension and integration into (third party-) services requiring semantic enrichment would be the logical next step.

2 Upstream works

2.1 Landscape analysis

The landscape analysis was conducted among the scientific domains of the nine WP6 use cases and aimed at identifying semantic artifacts (also called “semantic resources”) used by these domains. These artifacts can either be hosted on semantic artifact repositories, that allow for a “machine-actionable” access to those artifacts or just be available as isolated files in the form of ontologies or vocabularies, that reflect a broad agreement of the respective community but are not (yet) accessible in an actionable or FAIR manner. This analysis thus laid the groundwork for the collection of semantic artifacts to be included in the index. The identification of semantic artifacts that were not accessible in a machine-actionable manner led to the decision to set up an OntoPortal repository to host them.

2.1.1 Collection of semantic artifacts

The collection of artifacts for semantic interoperability started by interviewing domain experts from the nine WP6 use cases [2]. Within these interviews, the general aim of the task T5.5 was first explained to the interviewed partners. Then, they were asked to a) list any semantic artifacts in their use case or discipline that they knew of or applied themselves, b) list any repositories, websites, catalogs or other collections that host or refer to such artifacts, and c) list datasets used in their domain that make use of semantic technology for describing the actual payload data of a dataset in the form of a knowledge graph (like datasets in the LOD cloud [3]). The interviews were usually performed over several meetings with the interviewed partners, giving the interviewers and the interviewed the possibility to assess intermediate results, clarify questions with third parties, etc. Based on the interview results, the T5.5 team additionally conducted web-based literature searches to broaden the results indicated by the domain experts.

The semantic artifacts listed by the domain experts covered a broad range of types, a selection of typical types encountered is listed here:

1. various classification schemes, like the “library of congress subject headings” [4] as a general purpose example of a classification scheme, or the “ACM Computing Classification System” [5] as a domain specific example.
2. controlled vocabularies in legacy formats like “Core Controlled Vocabularies” [6] for use in intercomparison projects in geoscience.
3. file format descriptions like the “FASTQ format for sequencing data” [7] or the “SEED file format for seismic data” [8]
4. formal taxonomies in standards conformant SKOS [9], typically accessible through web browser (e.g. The Pactols Thesaurus [10])
5. repositories for SKOS taxonomies, accessible through browser and APIs (e.g. NERC Vocabulary Server (NVS) [11])

6. formal ontologies in standards conformant OWL [12], possibly accessible through OntoPortal appliances/repositories [13] which has a browser interface and an API (e.g. BioPortal [14]. Note: the OntoPortal appliance can also host SKOS taxonomies).

It is noteworthy that no dataset making use of semantic technology for describing the payload data (knowledge graph, LOD dataset), was identified by the use cases of WP6. This has at least two consequences: a) it limits the usage of formal (OWL-) ontologies in those use cases mainly to annotation purposes and b) it encourages the creation of annotation tools based on concept labels (`skos:prefLabel`, `skos:altLabel`, `rdfs:label`, ...) that support manual or automatic annotation of (data-) resources.

2.1.2 Evaluation of semantic artifacts

The evaluation of semantic artifacts for the index focused on artifacts that adhere to semantic web technology standards (namely 4.-6. in the list above) and for a start ruled out legacy artifacts that could enhance alignment and interoperability (namely 1.-3. in the list above). The evaluation process of the semantic artifacts mainly followed a systematic by Hugo et al. [15] (at the time of writing superseded by [16]) outlining 17 recommendations and 10 best practices for FAIR semantic artifacts. The list of criteria adopted (reproduced in the appendix) covers the ranges from metadata of the semantic artifact to technical information that are required to decide if the semantic artifact is suitable for the search index. The most prominent criteria in view of the index were:

- **C13: To what extent is the semantic artifact machine readable?**

There can be differences in the artifacts format and therefore the possible machine operations. If it is machine-visualizable (e.g. PDF) the semantic artifact can be visualized by a machine but the interpretation needs to be done by a human being. Therefore, it is not qualified for the usage in the index. The semantic artifact needs to be parsable (RDF).

- **C11: How weak or strong are the semantics of the artifact?**

If the semantic artifact fulfills the criterion of C13, the strength of the semantics is relevant. The higher the level of semantics, the more precise and rich in information the content is. This allows the user of the index to obtain greater details about the contents of the artifact. For the functions of the search index itself though, not much semantic strength is required, just that:

- the concepts, classes, etc in the semantic artifact have a unique identifier and annotations describing themselves, like `skos:prefLabel`, `skos:altLabel`, `rdfs:comment`,
- the semantic artifact also describes itself adequately (name, version, identifier, etc)

Which is the case even for a simple controlled vocabulary.

- **C14: Is the SA publicly available via a repository? / C8: License if provided**

For the reuse in this publicly funded project, it is very important that the semantic artifacts are publicly available and licensed in a way that they can be used by the community. In this

evaluation, semantic artifacts that were not publicly available or properly licensed, that were anyways the least common case, were discarded.

The evaluation of semantic artifacts showed that from the initially collected 38 candidates, 26 were qualified for further investigation. Based on the other evaluation criteria, 14 semantic artifacts from six WP6 use cases could be readily integrated into the search index. Most other artifacts require little work from their communities or maintainers to close the gap and make them adhere to semantic web standards (e.g. transform them from a legacy format to SKOS). Hopefully, the reward for closing this gap can be demonstrated by projects like this. The full result of the landscape analysis will be published separately [17].

All the semantic artifacts that were integrated into the search index were retrieved either from existing semantic artifact repositories or from EOSC-Pillar OntoPortal (see next subsection), where they were uploaded. The semantic artifact repositories from which the index was filled are listed in [Table 1](#) (see “Harvesting” section).

2.2 OntoPortal deployment

OntoPortal (<https://ontportal.org/>) is an open-source ontology repository service developed by the OntoPortal Alliance. The OntoPortal Alliance is a consortium of researchers with the aim of promoting semantic services in the scientific community. Therefore, OntoPortal enables the community to store, publish, share and explore ontologies in a single software solution. The OntoPortal repository is already commonly used in various domains. For example, it is the software behind BioPortal (<https://bioportal.bioontology.org/>) for the Biomedical domain, AgroPortal (<http://agroportal.lirmm.fr/>) for Agriculture and MatPortal (<http://matportal.org/>) for Material Science.

In the landscape analysis, it was found that relevant semantic artifacts from the use cases were not actionable through APIs but rather shared as isolated files on repositories like GitHub or websites. That means the semantic artifact itself conforms to the requirements for inclusion in the index, but can't be retrieved in a uniform manner from a harvesting service. The solution to overcome this hurdle and make all these semantic artifacts available for the search index was to set up an OntoPortal instance for the EOSC-Pillar project as an institutional ontology repository. This repository contains all semantic artifacts identified in the landscape analysis that are not already accessible through an API. Such an institutional repository for the EOSC is generally well suited for domains that do not have the capacity to operate their domain specific repository but nevertheless seek a central accessibility to their semantic artifacts. Another beneficial aspect of hosting semantic artifacts in an OntoPortal repository is that they become more FAIR: the repository makes intrinsic information of the semantic artifact more accessible, by e.g. displaying descriptions in a user-friendly GUI, enabling easy search etc. Besides this, the semantic artifact becomes more FAIR because it becomes accessible through OntoPortal's powerful and well documented API [18]. This is shown in [Figure 1](#). All ontology metadata become nicely visible in the GUI and (not visible in the figure) actionable through the API in the same degree of detail as they are displayed in the GUI.

OntoPortal enables by default to search for semantic artifacts by their name or acronym for direct access of specific ontology or taxonomy. If the user does not know the specific semantic artifact, but wants to search for a certain term, he can use the “Search for class” functionality and receive a list of

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corresponding concepts and the semantic artifacts where they are included. OntoPortal also keeps track of versions of semantic artifacts that were uploaded.

The EOSC-Pillar OntoPortal instance is publicly accessible via the URL <https://ontoportal.eosc-pillar.eu/>. It runs on a conventional server. In this prototyping phase, the EOSC-Pillar OntoPortal contains 21 Semantic Artifacts that include more than 1000 OWL classes and 78000 SKOS concept instances from the scientific domains of the EOSC-Pillar use cases. The upload of new semantic artifacts requires a registration of the user. Registration is restricted until the service is out of the prototyping phase.

The deployment of the OntoPortal made the WP6 use cases semantic artifacts that were not yet machine-actionable available for being harvested into the semantic index. It is now in principle open as a repository for SKOS and OWL semantic artifacts for the EOSC.

The screenshot shows the OntoPortal interface for a semantic artifact. The header includes the OntoPortal logo and navigation links: Ontologies, Search, Annotator, Recommender, Mappings, Login, and Support. The main content area displays the artifact's title and last upload date (March 31, 2022). Below this, there are tabs for Summary, Classes, Properties, Notes, Mappings, and Widgets. The 'Details' section provides information about the artifact, including its acronym (PACTOLS), visibility (Public), and a detailed description. The 'Metrics' section shows a table of statistics for the artifact. The 'Submissions' section shows a table of versions. The 'Visits' and 'Projects using PACTOLS' sections provide additional context.

Version	Released	Uploaded	Downloads
unknown (Parsed, Indexed, Metrics, Annotator)	09/24/2021	03/31/2022	SKOS CSV RDF/XML

Classes	Individuals	Properties	Maximum depth	Maximum number of children	Average number of children	Classes with a single child	Classes with more than 25 children	Classes with no definition
3	59,736	0	0	3	3	0	0	3

Figure 1: Detailed view of a semantic artifact in the EOSC-Pillar OntoPortal

3 The service architecture and its implementation

The service architecture aims at improving interoperability within and across domains through promotion of the FAIR principles, in particular principle I2 “(Meta)data use vocabularies that follow FAIR principles” [19]. The promotion of principle I2 is achieved by aggregating semantic artifacts into a single service that gives the scientific communities seamless access to a wealth of concepts and links them to the semantic artifacts that define those concepts. Technically speaking, by *semantic artifacts* we refer to OWL ontologies and SKOS thesauri. By *concept* we refer to instances of `skos:Concept`, subclasses of `owl:Thing` or subclasses of `owl:Thing`. Such a service architecture enables a number of downstream applications, like a “suggestion-as-you-type” application that can be used for interactive annotation of data or dataset metadata. The service architecture also allows for an automatic determination of best matching semantic concepts from keywords. In this section, we present the service architecture and its implementation in detail. We will call the service implementation a *search engine*. The section “Exploiting the service architecture” presents applications built on top of the service.

3.1 Overview

Search engines are information systems whose purpose is to facilitate the retrieval of information from a specific information corpus. Their operating principle is rather simple. First, a *query* is sent to the search engine. A query is an information retrieval request that can take different forms depending on the type of information to be retrieved. In this task, it is a simple string of text¹ that either (partially) matches or has some relationship with the concept to be retrieved. Then, the search engine returns a list of results, which are the pieces of information it considers the user is looking for, in this case **concepts**, arranged in descending order, from the ones assumed most relevant to the least relevant.

Search engines are typically engineered as a system that involves the following components, tasks or definitions:

1. **Information sources** - The information sources that the search engine should cover must be clearly determined. For example, in the typical search engines, that is, those aimed at humans browsing the world wide web, the information sources are websites, and one of the simplest ways to find new ones is to provide an initial set of websites and recursively follow their hyperlinks. However, in the search engine developed in this task, the information sources were manually selected by the developers. The criteria behind the decision were fixed by the *Landscape Analysis* that was carried out before starting to build the service.
2. **Harvesting** - Once the information sources have been located, then the individual units of information can be harvested from them. The harvesting is powered by the Federated FAIR Data Space Smart harvester. The Federated FAIR Data Space Smart Harvester is a service that was designed to retrieve metadata about datasets published in data repositories, but this task is very

¹ Sequence of characters, for example part of a word, a single word, multiple words, ...

similar to that of retrieving concepts from semantic artifact repositories, so the system was reused to also retrieve them. The REST API specification of semantic artifact repositories can be registered in the F2DS in the same way one would register data repositories (see EOSC-Pillar D5.6 [20]), so that they can subsequently be harvested by querying said API and then saving the corresponding API responses to a document-oriented database, MongoDB [21] for this service architecture.

3. **Normalization** - When it comes to retrieving information, not all details available on the source are always relevant or readily available. For example, it is useful to retrieve the text, images or videos displayed on a website, but retrieving the layout rarely is. In addition, depending on the type of queries that a search engine accepts, the original format of the information is not always the best for enabling its later retrieval. In the normalization process, irrelevant information is discarded, the relevant information retained, and the result possibly transformed to facilitate its later retrieval. In the service architecture implementation, this precisely means that the redundant or unnecessary information from the API responses is discarded, concepts are curated enforcing several logical constraints, and their schema is mapped to a common schema specifically tailored for the application.

Having this unified schema is of major importance, as the schema of the API responses can, in principle, be different for each semantic artifact repository, but the software that is used to build the search index replicates the structure of the input when it comes to interacting with the indexed data. If the information was not transformed to a common unified schema before ingestion, such interaction would have a great degree of artificial and unnecessary complexity.

Note that this means that for each different type of repository REST API that is registered, a different logic to transform the JSON payload into such a unified format is needed. It quickly became clear that implementing such normalization logic is labor-intensive. The process is not always easy to automate or even semi-automate because the original schemas can be fairly diverse, and in some cases, the needed information can be difficult to extract. At first, we considered using the F2DS Smart Harvester for this task, as it features the capability to map API responses to different schemas. However, some parts of the logic that had to be applied were very specific to the type of data being handled and the semantic artifact repository being harvested, so it was decided to implement the normalization logic as a separate software component.

The outcome of the normalization process is a collection on the MongoDB database with all concepts in a common schema.

4. **Index** - The desired functionality is to find concepts using text-based search queries that are related to them. To achieve that, it must be possible to retrieve the concepts related to the provided query from the information corpus at a reasonable speed. A solution to this problem is **building a search index**, which involves putting the data to be retrieved in a very large data structure that is heavily optimized for fast retrieval with specific query types. A good analogy of a search index is an English dictionary: it is very time-consuming to find a specific word in an

arbitrary book (e.g., a novel), but finding it in a dictionary is a piece of cake due to the words being arranged in alphabetical order. In this project, this task was handled by Elasticsearch, which is a search engine [22] that offers among others, two key features: very fast searches, especially of text data, and great scalability [23]. Elasticsearch is also document-oriented, and therefore is compatible with the data coming from the MongoDB instance.

5. **Search** – Once the data has been indexed by Elasticsearch, it is ready to answer queries. Answering a search query involves finding the units of information (concepts) that may have a relationship with the given query and then ranking them in descending order using a calculated score that represents the relevance of results. Depending on the specific scoring algorithm, it is possible that some scoring tasks may be executed even before receiving a query, for example as the search index is constructed or in the background, with the aim of pre-computing information that does not depend on the given query (e.g., the website importance in PageRank) [24]. In Task 5.5, this collection of activities is also handled by Elasticsearch. The scoring algorithms that Elasticsearch executes can be configured using a *Domain Specific Language* [25].

A graphical overview of the service architecture and its implementation is given in [Figure 2](#). The following subsections will explain the different components of the architecture and their implementation in detail.

Figure 2: Overview of the components of the service architecture

3.2 Harvesting

In order to create an index of concepts, it is necessary to harvest them from the semantic artifacts. In this task, this is done using the F2DS, which is a service designed to harvest JSON documents from repositories that are available through RESTful APIs services [26]. Using it, the information about semantic artifacts and the concepts they contain is harvested and stored into a MongoDB database so that further processing can be carried out later in the normalization process.

The F2DS was initially developed to harvest and unify metadata from data repositories [20] to a common format (namely DCAT [27]). However, because of the similarity to the task of the harvesting of semantic artifacts from semantic artifact repositories using a REST API, the tool has been reused for such purpose.

Figure 3: Illustration of the F2DS architecture showing the three main components: Data repository layer to register external repositories; the Smart Harvester layer to query the concepts of the SAs and the MongoDB to store the harvested concepts

The F2DS uses Java for its back-end part, and the front-end part is coded in Typescript via the Angular framework [28]. The deployment of these services is done using Kubernetes [29], which takes advantage of container technologies.

The F2DS solution consists, as shown in Figure 3, of two key layers: the data repository layer and the metadata harvester. The data repository layer can be operated by data producers through a specific interface for registering their repositories and for creating the description of each repository's API using the smartAPI [48] approach, derived from openAPI specification [30]. The metadata harvester layer, also called Smart Harvester, uses the registered API descriptions from the data repository layer to automatically build a dedicated client and the appropriate queries to gather the metadata stored in each repository. The harvested metadata is then stored to the MongoDB database and ready to be normalized before being indexed by the Elasticsearch service.

As an outcome of the Landscape Analysis, it was decided to harvest concepts from four ontology repositories: BioPortal [14], AgroPortal [31], EOSC-Pillar OntoPortal [32] and the NERC Vocabulary Server (NVS) [11].

The harvesting of these repositories resulted in 14,911,882 concepts collected and the service has the capacity to harvest approximately 7 million items per hour. Table 1 shows the amount of successfully harvested concepts by each repository (as of October 10, 2022):

Table 1. Results of harvesting

	ontologies	concepts
BioPortal	1,027	11,770,028
AgroPortal	147	2,955,031
EOSC-Pillar OntoPortal	19	62,849
NVS	288	123,974

In this task, the F2DS harvests not only information about concepts but also about the semantic artifact (also called *semantic resource*) where they are contained. Examples of the harvested data are illustrated in Figures 4 to 7. It is worth recalling that the schemas of the harvested API responses can be different depending on the source repository. Therefore, the harvested information must subsequently be normalized as explained in the next section. Even though four repositories were harvested, three of them (BioPortal, AgroPortal and EOSC-Pillar OntoPortal) are running the same software. Thus, they share a common schema, meaning that it is only needed to normalize two schemas.

```

{"_id": ObjectId("62b1d950d5d47c57c3eb41ff"),
  "repositoryId": "cdd8471e-b2a6-43a7-80f4-35cd8ddaa3e8",
  "url": "https://data.bioontology.org/ontologies/ITO/classes?page=1&userapikey=6b007238-a9bc-478d-8a53-cf87da6d697d",
  "document": {
    "synonym": ["Phylogeny"],
    "cui": [],
    "@type": "http://www.w3.org/2002/07/owl#Class",
    "prefLabel": "Phylogenetic tree",
    "semanticType": [],
    "obsolete": false,
    "definition": "A phylogenetic tree is usually constructed from a set of sequences from which an alignment (or data matrix) is calculated. See also 'Phylogenetic tree image'.",
    "@id": "http://edamontology.org/data_0872",
    "@context": {
      "synonym": "http://data.bioontology.org/metadata/skosynonym",
      "@vocab": "http://data.bioontology.org/metadata/",
      "definition": "http://data.bioontology.org/metadata/skosdefinition"
    },
    "links": {
      "mappings": "https://data.bioontology.org/ontologies/ITO/classes/http:3A%2F%2Fedamontology.org%2Fdata_0872/mappings",
      "notes": "https://data.bioontology.org/ontologies/ITO/classes/http:3A%2F%2Fedamontology.org%2Fdata_0872/notes",
      "ui": "http://bioportal.bioontology.org/ontologies/ITO?p=classes&conceptid=http:3A%2F%2Fedamontology.org%2Fdata_0872",
      "ontology": "https://data.bioontology.org/ontologies/ITO",
      "parents": "https://data.bioontology.org/ontologies/ITO/classes/http:3A%2F%2Fedamontology.org%2Fdata_0872/parents",
      "@context": {
        "mappings": "http://data.bioontology.org/metadata/Mapping",
        "notes": "http://data.bioontology.org/metadata/Note",
        "parents": "http://www.w3.org/2002/07/owl#Class"
      }
    }
  },
  "_class": "com.smartharvester.model.Ontologies"
}

```

Figure 4: A concept harvested from an OntoPortal-based repository (BioPortal). The fields of the BSON [33] document that are accessed during the normalization process (see [section 3](#)) are highlighted in yellow. Some parts have been omitted for brevity.

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```

{
  "id": ObjectId("62b1dd07d5d47c57c3f6a7bb"),
  "repositoryId": "cdd8471e-b2a6-43a7-80f4-35cd8ddaa3e8",
  "url": "https://data.bioontology.org/ontologies/ITO/classes?pagesize=5000&page=1&userapikey=6b007238-a9bc-478d-8a53-cf87da6d697d",
  "document": {
    "@type": "http://data.bioontology.org/metadata/OntologySubmission",
    "documentation": null,
    "description": "The Intelligence Task Ontology and Knowledge Graph (ITO) provides a comprehensive, curated model of artificial intelligence tasks, benchmarks and benchmark results, including the biomedical domain.",
    "creationDate": "2022-01-13T06:46:55-08:00",
    "version": "1.01 (PWC export dated 2021-06-16)",
    "@context": {
      "@vocab": "http://data.bioontology.org/metadata/",
      "hasOntologyLanguage": "http://data.bioontology.org/metadata/omvhasOntologyLanguage",
      ...,
      "status": "http://data.bioontology.org/metadata/omvstatus"
    },
    "submissionId": 15,
    "hasOntologyLanguage": "OWL",
    "contact": [
      {
        "name": "Omitted Name",
        "id": "https://data.bioontology.org/contacts/6f586a0b-7294-4c9d-978f-d85203f3774c",
        "email": "omitted@example.org"
      }
    ],
    "publication": null,
    "links": {
      "metrics": "https://data.bioontology.org/ontologies/ITO/submissions/15/metrics",
      "@context": {
        "metrics": "http://data.bioontology.org/metadata/OntologySubmission"
      }
    },
    "@id": "https://data.bioontology.org/ontologies/ITO/submissions/15",
    "ontology": {
      "summaryOnly": false,
      "acronym": "ITO",
      "flat": null,
      "@type": "http://data.bioontology.org/metadata/Ontology",
      "name": "Intelligence Task Ontology",
      "@links": {
        "notes": "https://data.bioontology.org/ontologies/ITO/notes",
        "projects": "https://data.bioontology.org/ontologies/ITO/projects",
        ...,
        "roots": "https://data.bioontology.org/ontologies/ITO/classes/roots",
        "@context": {
          "notes": "http://data.bioontology.org/metadata/Note",
          "projects": "http://data.bioontology.org/metadata/Project",
          ...,
          "views": "http://data.bioontology.org/metadata/Ontology"
        },
        "latest_submission": "https://data.bioontology.org/ontologies/ITO/latest_submission",
        "analytics": "https://data.bioontology.org/ontologies/ITO/analytics",
        ...,
        "views": "https://data.bioontology.org/ontologies/ITO/views",
      },
      "@id": "https://data.bioontology.org/ontologies/ITO",
      "administeredBy": ["https://data.bioontology.org/users/omitted"],
      "ontologyType": "https://data.bioontology.org/ontology_types/ONTOLOGY",
      "@context": {
        "@vocab": "http://data.bioontology.org/metadata/",
        "acronym": "http://data.bioontology.org/metadata/omvacronym",
        "name": "http://data.bioontology.org/metadata/omvname",
        "administeredBy": {
          "@type": "@id",
          "@id": "http://data.bioontology.org/metadata/User"
        },
        "ontologyType": {
          "@type": "@id",
          "@id": "http://data.bioontology.org/metadata/OntologyType"
        }
      }
    },
    "released": "2022-01-13T00:00:00+00:00",
    "homepage": "https://github.com/OpenBioLink/ITO/",
    "status": "production",
  },
  "class": "com.smartharvester.model.Ontologies"
}

```

Figure 5: A resource harvested from an OntoPortal-based repository (BioPortal). The fields of the BSON [33] document that are accessed during the normalization process (see [section 3](#)) are highlighted in yellow. Some parts have been omitted for brevity.

```

{"_id": ObjectId("63078f4185e4406e0aa5d65d"),
  "repositoryId": "1b0930f3-b0c5-415a-b5cb-2d612a70e873",
  "url": "http://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/S04/current?_profile=nvs&_mediatype=application/ld+json",
  "document": {
    "date": "2006-10-02 18:26:59.0",
    "identifier": "SDN:S04::S04140",
    "note": {"@value": "accepted", "@language": "en"},
    "inDataset": "http://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/.well-known/void",
    "authoredOn": "2006-10-02 18:26:59.0",
    "@type": "skos:Concept",
    "deprecated": false,
    "prefLabel": {
      "@value": "condensation nuclei counting",
      "@language": "en"
    },
  },
  "hasCurrentVersion": "http://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/S04/current/S04140/1/",
  "altLabel": "",
  "versionInfo": "1",
  "version": "1",
  "related": "http://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/P01/current/ATPCCNZZ/",
  "notation": "SDN:S04::S04140",
  "definition": {
    "@value": "Determination of the number per unit volume of air of ultra-fine particles, usually dust or salt,
    capable of forming aerosol particles through water vapour condensation.",
    "@language": "en"
  },
  "@id": "http://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/S04/current/S04140/",
  "broader": "http://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/S01/current/S0110/",
  "dc:identifier": "SDN:S04::S04140"
},
}_class": "com.smartharvester.model.Ontologies"
}

```

Figure 6: A concept harvested from the NERC Vocabulary Server. The fields of the BSON [33] document that are accessed during the normalization process (see section 3) are highlighted in yellow.

D5.5 Service architecture providing fast access to the concepts held within semantic artifacts

```
{
  "_id": ObjectId("63078f4185e4406e0aa5d72f"),
  "repositoryId": "1b0930f3-b0c5-415a-b5cb-2d612a70e873",
  "url": "http://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/S04/current?_profile=nvs&_mediatype=application/ld+json",
  "document": {
    "date": "2022-05-26 03:00:01.0",
    "creator": "British Oceanographic Data Centre",
    "@type": "skos:Collection",
    "prefLabel": "BODC parameter semantic model analytical method entity descriptions",
    "alternative": "Analytical method",
    "description": "Controlled vocabulary defining the terms that may be used for an analytical method entity (part of the how theme) in the BODC parameter semantic model.",
    "altLabel": "Analytical method",
    "versionInfo": "139 method",
    "title": "BODC parameter semantic model analytical method entity descriptions",
    "seeAlso": "https://github.com/nvs-vocabs/S04",
    "license": "https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/",
    "RE_RegisterManager": "British Oceanographic Data Centre",
    "RE_RegisterOwner": "British Oceanographic Data Centre",
    "inDataset": "http://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/.well-known/void",
    "authoredOn": "2006-10-02 18:26:59.0",
    "member": [
      "http://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/S04/current/S04278/",
      ...,
      "http://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/S04/current/S041023/"
    ],
    "publisher": "Natural Environment Research Council",
    "comment": "Governance for vocabularies used within the data centre",
    "@id": "http://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/S04/current/"
  },
  "_class": "com.smartharvester.model.Ontologies"
}
```

Figure 7: A resource harvested from the NERC Vocabulary Server. The fields of the BSON [33] document that are accessed during the normalization process (see section 3) are highlighted in yellow. The list of members of the resource was partially omitted for brevity.

3.3 Normalization

As described in the previous section, the information corpus is harvested by the F2DS Smart Harvester from the registered repositories of semantic artifacts and stored in a MongoDB instance. When registering a **semantic artifact repository** in the F2DS, a REST API specification for the repository needs to be provided. The F2DS Smart Harvester then sends requests to the repository using these specifications and stores the responses, which are expected to be received in JSON format, in the MongoDB. This implies that for each repository that is registered, the API responses will conform to a different schema specific to such repository. The normalization consists of transforming the information harvested from the different repositories into a common schema.

There are several reasons to do this, many of which have already been introduced in the previous sections:

- **From the information that is harvested, not all details are relevant or can be used for the search. The normalization selects what is relevant and discards everything else.** In addition, it is important to note that some information is in fact discarded even before the normalization process takes place, during the harvesting, either because of a lack of features of the API of the repository software, because the provided REST API specification is not complete, or because the F2DS cannot handle some corner cases of data schemas. An example is, the class hierarchy for concepts that belong to ontologies from repositories based on OntoPortal. This information is not relevant for building the index, and it is already discarded by the harvesting process.
- **The information has to be indexed and retrieved later by Elasticsearch.** Elasticsearch is, just like MongoDB, document²-oriented, and indices are built based on the document's fields.
 - Having different schemas for each semantic artifact repository involves building indices for several fields when in fact they contain the same type of information. This means one extra index lookup for each semantic artifact repository. But more importantly, the domain specific language used to query Elasticsearch [25] involves references to the fields. Having different schemas for different semantic artifact repositories means that the complexity of such queries will quickly grow with the number of repositories to the point of not being able to be easily understood and edited anymore.
 - Moreover, Elasticsearch does not play well with documents that are not *flat* (i.e. have multiple levels of nested keys): it causes a performance hit. The API responses from the repositories that were registered are not flat, and in some cases, there is information that should be indexed within the deeper levels.
- There is **information that needs to be reconstructed**:
 - As new versions of an ontology are released, the database and index accumulates several versions of the same concept, and for reasons that will be made clear in subsequent subsections (related to the interpretation point coming after this one), it is necessary to reconstruct the date at which the concept was published.

² The term document refers to JSON data structures in this context

- The ontology IRI [34] for concepts from repositories based on OntoPortal is not provided in the API responses, but this is key information when it comes to taking advantage of the search results depending on the application. Although it does not affect the specific use case described in the introduction, as soon as one wants to build upon this work, for example to search for datasets based on their annotations, this detail becomes relevant.
- **Information needs to be interpreted.** As the database and index accumulates several versions of the same concept when new versions of an ontology are published, concepts can become outdated or deprecated. They also have to be aggregated when they are defined in several semantic artifacts. Such operations are considered to be a part of the normalization process.

3.3.1 The common schema

As explained in previous sections, the main goal of the service architecture is to make the concepts and their associated semantic artifacts (selected in the Landscape Analysis) findable, and one of the criteria to make such selection was their machine-actionability or their availability in semantic artifact repositories. Concepts from artifacts satisfying any of the two requirements typically belong to a semantic artifact that may be an ontology (usually an OWL ontology or RDFS vocabulary) or a thesaurus (for example built using SKOS). All these ways to define a concept have in common that each concept gets assigned a unique identifier in the form of an IRI, can be annotated with information such as a human-readable label or a description, among others; and can even have logical constraints defined on them or connections to other concepts with varying degrees of expressiveness.

The common schema for concepts establishes the data model for a concept to be used within the search engine and implicitly declares what information from a concept is considered to be relevant for the application and any future work that has to build on it and what information is not. Rather than developing such a data model from scratch, a previous data model from the literature [35] was reused and adapted.

In this data model, the information that constitutes a concept is captured in a simple, flat JSON document with the fields listed below. Mandatory fields are written in **bold**, whereas optional fields are written in *italics*.

- **iri**: The IRI that serves as unique identifier for the concept.
- **label**: Human readable (main) label of the concept. Unless unavailable, expect it to be the English label.
- *short form*: A short form of the concept's main label.
- *description*: Description or definition of the concept.
- *synonyms*: List of synonym labels for the concept.
- *domains*: Domains to which the concept belongs, according to the Frascati Manual descriptors of domains [36].
- *resource iri*: The IRI of the resource that this concept belongs to.
- *resource name*: The name of the resource that this concept belongs to.
- *resource acronym*: An acronym for the resource to which the concept belongs.
- *resource date*: Date on which the resource was released.

- *resource version*: The version of the resource to which this concept belongs to.
- *resources reusing*: The IRIs of other resources reusing this concept.
- *resources reusing acronyms*: Acronyms of the resources that reuse this concept.
- **harvested from**: An URL pointing to the resource where the concept was retrieved from. The difference with respect to “resource iri” field is that “resource iri” is defined by the author of the resource within the resource file, whereas “harvested from” refers to the location where the resource file was actually found.
- **ui link**: An URL pointing to a website where a human may visualize the concept or put it in context with respect to other concepts.

```

{
  "iri": "http://edamontology.org/data_0872",
  "label": "Phylogenetic tree",
  "description": "A phylogenetic tree is usually constructed from a set of sequences from which an alignment (or data matrix) is calculated. See also 'Phylogenetic tree image'.",
  "synonyms": ["Phylogeny"],
  "domains": [],
  "resource iri": "https://identifiers.org/ito:ontology",
  "harvested from": "https://data.bioontology.org/ontologies/ITO",
  "ui link":
"http://bioportal.bioontology.org/ontologies/ITO?p=classes&conceptid=http%3A%2F%2Fedamontology.org%2Fdata_0872",
  "resource name": "Intelligence Task Ontology",
  "resource acronym": "ITO",
  "resource date": "2022-01-13T00:00:00.000Z",
  "resource version": "1.01 (PWC export dated 2021-06-16)",
  "resources reusing": ["http://edamontology.org"],
  "resources reusing acronyms": ["EDAM"]
}

```

Figure 8: Example of concept in its normalized form.

As it can be seen, this model for normalized concepts is actually not as formal as in an ontology or a thesaurus. It just captures the information that is considered relevant, discarding everything else. In fact, it was already complicated to fill some of the fields with data: the *short form* and *domains* field, are in fact always left empty for the concepts considered in our work, as this information is typically not provided by the ontology publishers and no reliable workaround was developed within the project to determine a reliable value for them.

A more formal, machine-readable version of this data model, that also includes detailed per-field examples, is provided as an attachment published together with this document (in JSON Schema format). Nevertheless, an example for a concept in this normalized form is also provided in [Figure 8](#).

It is noteworthy to remark that the fields that refer to the metadata of the resource (i.e. semantic artifact) that the concept belongs to are important for building upon the work done in this task. A great example of how, for example, the resource IRI can be used, is to extend a dataset repository to make its users able to search for datasets using a concept from an ontology, so that also datasets annotated with a subclass of the concept selected for the search are displayed. One possible implementation of such functionality could be realized by retrieving this additional information from the file where the ontology is defined, and querying it in a triplestore. However, this is just an example, and depending on the specific semantic artifact repositories being harvested and the engineering tradeoffs to be made, implementations that do not require the resource IRI are also possible.

3.3.2 Details about the harvested data

The data harvested by the F2DS is the starting point of the transformation to the common schema that was just described. Examples of the harvested data for each kind of semantic artifact repository were shown in the previous section (Figures 4 to 7). In such examples, the parts that were used to construct the normalized version are highlighted in yellow. A general overview on how the normalization process itself was performed in practice is provided in the next subsection. As previously explained, the following semantic artifacts repositories were registered in the F2DS and harvested:

- BioPortal [14]
- AgroPortal [31]
- EOSC-Pillar OntoPortal [32]
- NERC Vocabulary Server (NVS) [11]

The first three are running the OntoPortal software described in section 3, while the NERC Vocabulary service is based on VocPrez [37]. This implies that there are only two different APIs and two different response schemas to be handled.

As it can be observed in Figure 8, many fields refer to the metadata of the resources that the concepts belong to. Thus, to have the necessary information to fill the fields of the normalized schema, it is necessary to query the APIs of OntoPortal and VocPrez not only for concepts, but also for such resource metadata. After that, the API responses related to concepts need to be matched with the API responses related to resources they belong to. In addition, for the two kinds of API that were registered, we identified the following issues:

- The fields “domains” and “short form” had to be left empty for all concepts, because they simply cannot be filled due to a lack of information in the API responses.
- For NERC data, the resource acronym is not available within the API responses.
- For OntoPortal data, the **resource IRI is not available**. OntoPortal gives its own identifier to the resources, but they do not coincide with the identifier assigned by the author of the resource, which for example, for OWL ontologies, is where it is supposed to always be available [38].
- If the concept is duplicated in several semantic artifacts, this is not reflected on the API responses for each single instance. To fill such fields it is necessary to agglomerate the harvested data.

Details on how concept API responses are matched with the API responses related to resources they belong to and on how the concerns listed above are addressed in practice are provided in the next subsection.

3.3.3 Normalization pipeline

A simple data processing pipeline was written in Python to carry out the normalization procedure, which needs to run on a machine with access to the MongoDB instance where the harvested data is saved. A general overview of the pipeline is provided in Figure 9. The regular execution of this pipeline was scheduled using Apache Airflow [39].

Figure 9: General overview of the tasks and stages (tasks that can be executed in parallel) that make up the data normalization pipeline as shown in the Apache Airflow [39] control panel. “NormalizationEnd” and “End” are dummy operators [40] that serve to group the tasks in the “normalization” stage and to mark the end of the pipeline respectively. To fully understand this figure, It is recommended to have a second look after having read the whole section where it is located.

The pipeline starts with a so-called **“normalization” stage** (not to be confused with the whole normalization process), which consists of one Apache Airflow task for each registered semantic artifact repository: “AgroPortal”, “BioPortal”, “EOSCPillarOntoPortal”, and “NVS”. Whenever two or more repositories share a common API specification, the Python code for the tasks is also shared. For each repository, its corresponding task goes over the harvested concepts that are stored in the database and maps them to the normalized schema (the *resources reusing* and *resources reusing acronyms* are still left blank at this stage). The results are saved to a different collection from the MongoDB (the *normalized concepts collection*), which may already contain normalized concepts from previous executions. The object ids of the concepts, and thus their harvesting dates, are retained also in this other collection. When the tasks successfully finish their execution, a timestamp of their starting date is saved so that on the next execution all harvested concepts older than such date can be skipped. This means that for each run of the pipeline, only newly harvested concepts are processed.

During this “normalization” stage, filling the fields related to the normalized model that are related to the concept itself is quite straightforward. Complexity is more significant when it comes to mapping the concepts to the resources they come from, as well as when extracting some fields related to the resource information.

The matching of the concepts to their resources (i.e. semantic artifacts), made with the scope of retrieving their resource information, is done using the following two facts. One of the inputs used to construct the MongoDB object id of a new document is the time it is created, and this information can be retrieved back from the object id. Therefore, for each harvested object, the harvesting time is known.

Moreover, the publication date of the resources is always known. Since the concepts available on the repositories during harvesting are always those that correspond to the latest version of a resource, concepts have to be mapped to the most recently published version of the resource whose publication date is earlier than the harvesting time of the concept.

A major complication when extracting the resource information is caused by the fact that OntoPortal-based semantic artifact repositories do not return the resource IRI fixed by the resource's author, neither in the API responses to requests for concepts nor resources, but an internal IRI is assigned by the OntoPortal software. The only way to obtain the resource IRI fixed by the author is to download the resource and read it. This is precisely what has been done. As the size of many of these resources is not negligible, it is infeasible to download them often. Therefore, a cache has been implemented also for this purpose: each time that a resource is downloaded and its resource IRI read, this information is saved to a cache and linked to the OntoPortal resource identifier and publication date of the resource. This avoids, for example, having to re-download the resources if the pipeline execution is interrupted or fails, or if one wishes to re-normalize all harvested concepts rather than just the newly harvested ones. OntoPortal enforces relatively few constraints on what can be uploaded as a resource: in a repository one may find a heterogeneity of formal languages describing the resources, serialization formats, and applied modifications (e.g. compression of the resource files). It was difficult to cover all this variety, and therefore the resource IRI retrieval is constrained just to a few cases from this varied landscape. Whenever retrieving the resource IRI of a resource is not supported, it is just left blank. The harvested from field is always available as a fallback to retrieve the resource file if the need arises.

After the “normalization” stage, another **stage** aimed to delete concepts that are no longer of interest is executed (the so-called “**non-existent concepts**”). At this stage, the object ids in the MongoDB collection where harvested concepts are stored, are scanned and compared to the object ids in the MongoDB collection where the normalized concepts are stored. Any items that are not in the first collection but are in the second are deleted from the second collection. This stage of the pipeline works as an external control mechanism that can manage the set of concepts stored in the normalized concepts collection.

The next stage is the **deletion of outdated concepts**. There, concepts are aggregated by *iri* and *resource iri* fields (or as a fallback, *harvested from*), and the concept with the newest resource date is chosen. This clears up duplicates, including the ones that appear when in-between runs of the harvesting process a new version of an ontology is published.

This stage is then followed by the deletion of **deprecated concepts**. Deprecated concepts are concepts that were available in a resource, but have been removed in a later version. To achieve this, the outputs of the previous stage of the pipeline are compared to the latest publication date of their resource. If there is a version of the resource that is newer than the one currently associated with the concept, this means that the concept is deprecated and can be deleted.

The last stage of the pipeline is the **grouping step**: concepts are aggregated by *iri*. The fields *resource iri* and *resource acronym* are selected at random from one of the elements that are part of the aggregation, and the rest are relocated to the *resources reusing* and *resources reusing acronyms* fields. This time, modifications are not made in-place in the normalized concepts collection. Rather, the results of this

stage are always **saved** to a **new collection** (that is overwritten if exists), **from which Elasticsearch** later **ingests** the data to be indexed.

3.4 Index

After the normalization process, the concepts are ready to be collected in a **search index**. Elasticsearch was the software chosen for this task. It features both the capability to build the search index and use it to answer search queries, and also stands out for its performance and scalability, meeting the requirements that are expected for this kind of system:

- (i) fast search through a high-availability service,
- (ii) can scale as the number of concepts harvested and users grow,
- (iii) has the ability to perform full text searches (defined as a natural-language document identification that satisfies a query and sorts them by a similarity score).

3.4.1 Infrastructure

The infrastructure bearing this load (refer to [Figure 10](#)) had to meet the following constraints: ensure a fast text search, be as intuitive as possible for the user, support multiple simultaneous queries and be used without service interruption. These requirements are met by the basic architecture of an Elasticsearch cluster of 3 uniform nodes, i.e., each one managing the data search and the internal management of the cluster.

Figure 10: Index infrastructure

This cluster construction has several interesting properties: if the number of concepts increases drastically or the number of searches per second increases as well, pushing the cluster to its limits, a

simple solution would be to use the scalability properties of the cluster by increasing the number of nodes.

Another interesting property of the cluster is its resilience to failures: searches are performed on indexes, which are divided into small fragments on the nodes, these fragments being themselves replicated. Thus, if one node of the cluster fails, the other two nodes will be fully capable of responding to user queries. The information contained in the indexes is distributed in several copies within the cluster, which allows the high availability of the service, making it possible to carry out searches even in the event of a failure of an element.

3.4.2 Indexing

An index in Elasticsearch is document oriented. A document is an entity of information composed of fields focused around a theme. In the instance for this service architecture, each field is a key-value doublet and the whole document in its structure will have to respect the file and data exchange format called JSON (JavaScript Object Notation). An example of the kind of documents that have to be indexed by Elasticsearch (the normalized concepts) is available in [Figure 8](#).

Before one starts putting documents in the index though, it is necessary to analyze the structure of the document and anticipate what fields the user may want to search and what is expected as a result, even discussing it directly with him/her if needed. Will the user want to find the documents whose key "iri" has exactly the value "http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/DOID_0060473" or the most relevant documents whose "description" field contains "immunological defect"? Or will the goal be to find the documents with resources dated before May 2020? Will it make sense to look for an exact match on "resource name" but also search for all documents for which this field contains the word "Ontology"? This step is called (in the Elasticsearch context) mapping [\[41\]](#), and consists of defining the data type for each key of the document. The selected mapping determines how the different fields of the document are stored and indexed.

The creation of the index, called **indexing**, is performed during an ingestion step in which a data collector will retrieve the collection of concepts from the MongoDB database and add them to the index. This data collector is called Logstash [\[42\]](#) (part of the Elastic stack [\[43\]](#)) and acts as a data streaming pipeline, that is, an Input-Filter-Output process that can ingest a multitude of data sources (Input) which in our case is MongoDB (but a large number of sources can be processed), clean and enrich each event with relevant information (Filter) and route data into the Elasticsearch engine (Output) as illustrated in [Figure 11](#).

Figure 11: Input, Filter, Output process

The data collector retrieves all the concepts through a query to the concept collection database. Each of the results will then enter the pipeline by being considered and treated as an independent event which

will be forwarded during the output stage towards its destination, namely, to be indexed in the form of a document in the search engine. One of the advantages of a data collector is the management of the backpressure phenomenon [44] in order to improve reliability and resilience. On a practical level, this involves the use of a queue persisted to disk that will store events until it is full. At this point, it is as if the output part of the pipeline puts back pressure on the input to stall data flowing into the upstream part. Also, this queuing system acts like a buffer that can come in handy when the output search engine is unavailable or too busy to handle data ingestion.

3.4.3 Query answering

Once the index has been constructed, Elasticsearch can use it to answer search queries. Queries are provided to Elasticsearch using its *Domain Specific Language* [25], which has great expressivity. Moreover, the query also serves as input for Elasticsearch's scoring algorithms, thus determining the score that is given to the results. A few, but not the only examples of what it enables are: to define the fields to search in, give them different weights, or to require that results are present in several fields at once.

Of course, it is not meant for the end-user of the service architecture to construct queries using this Domain Specific Language. As shown in the next section, the idea is that the user simply has to write a string of text in a search box on a graphical user interface, although under the hood, this query is translated to this Domain Specific Language for queries, and sent to the Elasticsearch to be processed.

Such graphical user interface is part of the F2DS (see next section) and the communication with Elasticsearch happens through a simple REST API developed in the task (that we called *search API*), secured by an API key, that listens for requests containing the text to be searched, uses such text to fill a query template in the Domain Specific Language, passes the request to Elasticsearch, and finally routes back the results to the graphical user interface. The motivation for such a REST API is to avoid directly exposing the Elasticsearch service in order to reduce the attack surface of the whole architecture. The time required for answering a search query generated by the F2DS interface is of the order of a hundred milliseconds. This corresponds to an average of about 100 milliseconds per API request that includes network exchanges, plus the time it takes Elasticsearch to process the query (about ten milliseconds). This time is satisfactory enough to be considered instantaneous for human sensitivity, and makes the index suitable for applications that require rapid and repeated feedback.

4 Exploiting the service architecture

The service architecture presented in the previous chapter can be used to power a variety of functionalities. This section presents the specific functionalities that were exploited in this task and how they were integrated into the F2DS to drive a workflow for semantic annotation of datasets. The demo-implementation shows how the service architecture that was built, featuring a search index that collates semantic artifacts from the community-driven semantic artifact repositories as well as other sources (like web pages, code repositories, etc.) that were deemed valuable for the different EOSC-Pillar use-cases, allows seamless access to the concepts and the semantic artifacts they belong to.

4.1 As-you-type-suggestions and automatic annotation

The service architecture that was built was used to provide two functionalities revolving around the annotation of datasets published in the F2DS (see deliverable 5.6 [20]):

1. **As-you-type suggestions to annotate datasets** - The user types a string of text in a search box to query the search engine, and the engine returns a list of best matching concepts, continuously updated as the user types. From this list, the user selects the concepts that are deemed most adequate to add them as annotations asserting that the dataset has some relationship to them, thus improving its findability.
2. **Automatic annotation of datasets** - If a dataset has been previously annotated with plain text keywords, such keywords are used to query the search engine for concepts and the best matching result for each keyword is used to annotate the dataset.

In these two applications, the inputs provided are strings of text, but as described in the previous section, queries must be provided to Elasticsearch using its Domain Specific Language [25] and also serve as input for Elasticsearch's scoring algorithms. Thus, the way in which such inputs are transformed into an Elasticsearch query is of crucial importance, as it determines the quality of the results. For this purpose, a query template (shown in [Figure 13](#), part of Appendix II), was designed and included in the code of the search API. Feedback from a collaborating scientist from the WP6 use cases was taken into consideration during the design to improve the search outcomes.

4.2 Integration into the F2DS repository

The search engine is used in the context of Task 5.1 [20]. The goal of this task is to create a federated FAIR data space from multi-disciplinary data repositories by harvesting, unifying and enriching the datasets with semantic artifacts. With the aim of addressing this last need, the search index service was integrated so that it can be used to improve the FAIRness of the harvested datasets. Thereby, the F2DS is connected to the search index through the search API service introduced in the last section for the purpose of finding matching terms from semantic artifacts.

During the F2DS dataset publishing process, the F2DS allows to recover the free-text keywords if there are any associated with the dataset by using the mapping description and more specifically the jsonPath

corresponding to the DCAT [27] property `dcat:keyword`. If this is the case, the F2DS queries the search engine to retrieve a list of concepts related to each keyword and selects by default the concept with the highest score from the response (**automatic annotation of datasets**). The user has the choice of refining the outcome using this list: either selecting a different result, annotating the dataset with additional terms, or even deciding not to annotate the dataset, according to his position regarding the available concepts.

If the harvested dataset does not have any associated keywords, or just if it is the wish of the user, new concepts can be retrieved by typing a keyword in a search box to add additional annotations (**as-you-type-suggestions**).

The unique identifiers of the retrieved semantic concepts are then added to the metadata scheme of the dataset to enrich it, using the DCAT property `dcat:theme`. All these features are integrated in the user interface shown in [Figure 12](#), so the hurdle for users of the scientific domain to benefit from the developments of this task are as low as possible.

enter a value with at least 4 characters

Phylogeny visualisation

label	definition	synonyms
Phylogeny visualisation	Visualise a phylogeny, for example, render a phylogenetic tree.	

GENOME

label	definition	synonyms	score	harvested from
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Genome	Representation of a genome. Genomic features that constitute the genome may be linked via one or more "Collection", "Catalog", "Contig", "Scaffold" or "File" instances. "Genome" can be used for describing data contents of the "genome-build" and "sequencing-scope" pragmas in GVF files.		132.16	agroportal
<input type="checkbox"/> Genome	Representation of a genome. Genomic features that constitute the genome may be linked via one or more "Collection", "Catalog", "Contig", "Scaffold" or "File" instances. "Genome" can be used for describing data		132.16	bioportal

Figure 12: User Interface for mapping the dataset to a keyword. Results are sorted by a matching score.

5 Conclusion and outlook

The objective of EOSC-Pillar's Task 5.5 was to build a service architecture that increases the FAIRness of the semantic artifacts used by the scientific communities represented by the nine EOSC-Pillar use cases collected into WP6 and provides fast access to the concepts held within them. To achieve this goal, a Landscape Analysis was conducted to identify which semantic artifacts had to be considered and were feasible to integrate in the service architecture. Then, an EOSC-Pillar semantic artifact repository based on OntoPortal was deployed to increase the accessibility of the semantic artifacts that needed it (i.e. by making them machine-actionable). Finally, thanks to the F2DS, a data processing pipeline and Elasticsearch, a search engine making the whole collection of concepts from said semantic artifacts quickly and easily findable was put into service. The service architecture was integrated into the F2DS user interface to power a workflow for adding semantic annotations to scientific datasets, demonstrating what can be achieved when FAIRer semantic artifacts are readily available. Several design considerations were made to make it easier to build upon the system in the future.

The outcome of the task has successfully proven the success and high performance of the chosen approach, as well as its usefulness for practical applications. However, there is still room to improve some aspects of the system architecture related to its performance. At the moment, when new concepts become available on the repositories, the normalization pipeline only processes the newly harvested concepts, but the search index has to be rebuilt from scratch. A better solution would be to update the search index by comparing the existing concepts with the concepts to ingest in order to determine which are the new ones. Another improvement could be the parallelization of the normalization pipeline.

Furthermore, the dataset annotation workflow immediately shows in which direction to go in order to build upon the results of this task. Access to concepts held within semantic artifacts has been made simple and fast to the point that a researcher can easily use them as metadata for the datasets that they publish. The next obvious step is developing a service that can make use of these annotations to find datasets. As semantic artifacts encode knowledge about the interrelationships between the concepts in them, the potential is huge: datasets can be annotated with very precise terms, but searches with a wide scope can be performed just referring to the general term. Another possibility is locating datasets that combine an intersection of topics, that can again be referred to with more general terms that the dataset was annotated with.

As explained throughout the document, the service can be accessed through the F2DS web interface [\[45\]](#), during the F2DS data repository mapping. At present, the partners involved do not plan to maintain the service after the end of the project, but the source code of the F2DS is publicly available and distributed under open source licenses [\[46\]](#) [\[47\]](#).

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7 Appendix I. Landscape analysis evaluation criteria

Table 2: List of all evaluation criteria and the possible answers. Please note that the Landscape Analysis uses the term SA also for what in this document is known as “semantic artifact repository”.

Criterion	Criterion Title	Manifestation/Comment
c1	Name of the Semantic Resource/Alias	text
c2	Is the semantic resource a repository?	Y, N
c3	In which UC is the SA used?	text
c4	Application/Research Domain of the SA	text / Frascati manual ([36]) conform descriptors of domains
c5	Under which URL is the HTML visualization of the SA available?	URL
c6	Short description of the SA and its usage	text
c7	Source of short description (URL) if not written ourselves	URL
c8	License if provided	text
c9	Last updated	Date YYYY/MM/DD
c10	Preferred namespace URI if applicable	text, n/a (does not apply), unknown (not provided) unknown if applies
c11	How weak or strong is the SA?	Glossary/List, Hierarchy, Thesaurus, SKOS, Formal Ontology (Formal Ontology/RDFS), n/a
c12	To what extent is the SA machine-readable?	machine-visualisable (e.g. HTML, PDF file), machine-parseable (e.g. XML/JSON file), machine-actionable (e.g. RDF/SKOS file). If repository: machine-actionable (e.g. API)
c13	In which format is the artifact saved/ available?	file type of downloadable artefact if available
c14	Is the SA publicly available via a repository?	Y, N/unknown, SR (Semantic Repository)
c15	Under which URL is the file download of the SA available?	URL, n/a
c16	Has the SA been developed by the UC?	Y, N, n/a
c17	Is there documentation material available for understanding the SA?	Y (URI), N, n/a (unknown)
c18	Is the SA accessible via an API?	Y, (URI), N/unknown
c19	Can this SA be recommended for automatic concept harvesting via F2DS?	Y/N
c20	Comment or reasoning for statement under item 19	text

8 Appendix II. Elasticsearch query template

```
{
  "bool": {
    "must": {
      "multi_match": {
        "query": input,
        "type": "most_fields",
        "fields": [
          "document.label^10",
          "document.synonyms",
          "document.description",
        ]
      }
    },
    "should": {
      "match": {
        "document.resource name": {
          "query": input_resource_name,
        }
      }
    }
  }
}
```

Figure 13: Query template used to transform the user's input into an Elasticsearch query for the two applications described in the section "Exploiting the service architecture": as-you-type suggestions to annotate datasets and automatic annotation of datasets. The text **input** is replaced by the input for the user, while **input_resource_name** is unused and its value is always set to **null**. The **label** field is weighted to have much more importance than the **synonyms** or **description** fields.